

Indian Federalism: Various Dimensions

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Abstract

Democracy has been established as a way of life in the 21st century, where continuous efforts are being made to increase public participation in the political system. At present, various means are being used to increase public participation and participation of common people in the process of decision making, so that political power can be decentralised. So that the misuse of power can be minimized and the dictatorial system can be prevented from growing and the rights of the common people can be ensured. In the present paper, along with the theoretical discussion of federalism, the nature of federalism in India and its various forms are described. Analytical and critical method has been used in the present study.

Key words: Federalism, Federalism, Centre-State Relations, Centralized Federalism, Cooperative Federalism, Competitive Federalism, Decentralization, Autonomy, Constitution.

Introduction

Federalism is such a concept that nurtures the proper harmony of rights, all these words union, federalism and federalism in some way or the other denote such an organization, where many political units share the same political system and decentralization of power. Federalism replaces such a pattern of governance, in which the division of powers is done by the constitution between the Union and the units, so that both of them, while remaining autonomous in their respective jurisdictions, work for the progress and welfare of the common man. Can work for and citizens can use their rights and freedoms rationally.

In the modern era, federalism is not just in the political sense, it is also known as financial, cultural, international federalism. As a result of which it is also emerging as a broad concept or mindset, which has the ability to keep different units and opinions together. Due to these reasons, federalism seems to be closer to democracy. Many experiments have been done with federalism in the modern political environment, due to which its form is continuously being refined.

Meaning and Definition of Federalism

The origin of the word federalism is from the Latin word '*Thvamacenesse*' which means agreement or treaty. Federalism is, in principle, a constitutional compromise between regional interests and national interests. Federalism has been defined by various political thinkers as follows:

According to K.C. Wheer, in a federal system, "*both the general and the provincial government are in direct contact with the citizens and every citizen lives under the rule of two governments.*"

According to Corey and Abraham - "*There is such a duality of federal government which is based on regional and functional division of powers with a view to coordinate unity with diversity.*"

Daniel J. Elajra says that "*The federal system organizes and integrates different polities into such a larger political system in which each political system remains connected with its basic political state.*"

On the basis of the above definitions, it is clear that the federal system is based on diarchy and different units follow the principle of decentralization of power among themselves. In a federal system, two forms of government exist, which are known by different names in different political systems. Both these governments contribute to the building of the nation-state by performing their

respective tasks under the umbrella of a political system, so that the nation can be strengthened internally and externally by fulfilling the aspirations of the people.

Stages of Federalism

If the historical perspective of federalism is observed, it is known that federalism is a very ancient concept, although its form in ancient times was different from the form of modern-day federalism. Theoretically and systematically, the beginning of federalism is believed to be from the 'Philadelphia Conference' (1787), where 13 states together formed a new union of a new government so that it could strengthen its external security.

The main two stages or types of formation of federalism are-

1. Coming Together Federalism

This type of federation is formed by different states. Different states together form a centre. In this system all the states get equal rights. In this system, the existence of states/provinces is primary because states/provinces only form the union and determine its jurisdiction. Generally, in this type of federalism, the powers of the Union are defined and the rest of the powers are exercised by the provinces (especially the residuary powers). We can see this type of federalism in the context of America.

2. Holding Together Federalism

This is another means of establishing a federal system. In this process of union formation, the existence of the union is primary, that is, the union forms various units. In this system, the position of the units is somewhat weak because the power and jurisdiction of the units is determined by the union and most of the powers (especially the residuary powers) are exercised by the union. In this type of system, the centre is more important, and the federal system is not the result of any agreement. For example - Canada, India.

Formation or Origin of the Indian Union

The Indian federal system is inspired by Canada in terms of construction, where federalism was a product of the British era and not of any agreement. In India, under the Government of India Act of 1935, a federal system was established at the federal level, in which all powers were considered to be the source of the British Crown. The Government of India Act of 1935 divided the powers between the Union and the provinces. Powers at the federal and provincial levels were divided into transferred and reserved categories. Some main subjects were given autonomously to the provinces, but still the federal government had some important powers, such as the power to give directions to the provinces, the privileges of the governor, etc. Therefore, from the beginning, the position of the Union has been strong in the Indian federal system. This statement of the Joint Parliamentary Committee is important for understanding the federal system in India -

In converting a unitary state into a federation, we are taking a step which has no precedent in history. A federation usually results from an agreement between independent or autonomous governments. These governments surrender part of their sovereignty or autonomy to the new central organization, at present the provinces of British India are not autonomous because they are under the administrative and legislative control of the government and the authority, they exercise is given to them by the Council, the Governor. Received under the rule making power of the General. We find it necessary to create autonomous units by an Act and by the same Act combine them to form a federation

Therefore, it is clear that the Indian federal system is fundamentally different from the American federal system. According to the circumstances federalism has been made a part of the Indian system. Dicey believes that the Indian princely states "lacked the spirit of federation", but due to political upheavals and equations, their decision changed and they had to become a part of the Indian Union. Even after following the integrated model of union building, importance was also given to the rights of the states in the Indian constitution. According to Basu, "The credit of bringing the princely

states into the federal system is not so much to the framers of the constitution as they are to place the other units of the federation on an equal footing under a single constitution." is unique.

Indian Federalism: Historical Background

The beginning of federalism in India is believed to be from the colonial rule. The form of the Indian federal system today is inspired by the colonial governance system. The British government adopted a centralized system to rule India in 1773, but in the Government of India Act 1919, diarchy was established in the provinces, in which the states had laws on certain subjects. The right to create was given. Like- education, health, agriculture etc. Under this act, the central control over the states was relaxed.

The Government of India Act 1935 is considered a milestone for Indian federalism. With this, the unitary rule going on in India was ended. Though the part relating to the federation remained ineffective, yet the part relating to provincial autonomy was made effective in 1937 for India. This act divided the legislative powers between the provincial and central legislatures. The provinces were not delegated to the central government in their enclaves but were as independent units of administration.

Lord Simon has called the federal system a way of Hindu-Muslim harmony. Certainly, due to religious, regional, conflicts in India, such a system was appropriate where efforts were being made to balance the autonomy of different states and the power of the centre. Therefore, even before independence, a kind of federal structure existed, which was also used to lay the foundation of the Indian federal system. After independence, it was ensured that India was an indestructible union of destructive states, so that territorial integrity could be maintained. Article 1 addresses India as a 'Union of States'. There are different opinions regarding the tendency of centralization in the Indian Union, but some of the main reasons behind the centralized system are as follows-

- Unorganized India and the circumstances at that time
- The inclination of the Congress leadership towards federal rule
- Maintaining integrity.
- Administrative facilities etc.

The federal structure run smoothly under the charismatic leadership of Nehru until the 1960s, but after the defeat of the Congress in the 1967 assembly elections, there were rapid changes in the federal relationship, with other parties forming governments in the states. From here the era of struggle between the powers of the centre and the state started. The main issues in these were, the use of President's rule by the government, the role of the governor in the states, etc. All these controversies reduced the loyalty of the states towards the centre. After this, in the era of coalition governments in the 1980s and 90s, regional parties played a decisive role and the central authority felt the need for the cooperation of the states, which was a good sign for Indian federalism. Apart from this, in the era of liberalisation, globalization and privatization, the financial autonomy of the states has been greatly strengthened. But this also shows the disparity between the states. Thus, the form of federal system in India has been cooperative and competitive from centralized.

Nature of Indian Federalism

If the constitutional terminology is taken into account, the word federalism has not been used anywhere, but the feeling of integration has been given a prominent place by using the word "Union of States". Following are the main features of the Indian federal system -

1. Written Constitution
2. Constitutionally Separation of Powers (7th Schedule)
3. Mixture of rigid and flexible constitution
4. Provision of single citizenship
5. Single Judiciary
6. One Constitution

7. Residuary Powers with the Centre
8. Centralized system in emergency
9. Strong Centre

Due to the above characteristics, the Indian Union has been termed as "quasi-federal" by K.C. Wheer. Which means that the characteristics of both unitary and federal systems are present in the same system.

There are many views regarding the complete federalism of Indian federalism, which according to Dr. R. Bargi can be divided into two categories-

1. Indian system is federal - Charles H. Alexandrovich, AL What's, Rashid Uddin Khan.
2. The Indian system is not federal. K. C. Whear, Ivor Jennings, K. Santhanam.

First opinion: The Indian system is federal

According to Charles H. Alexandrovich, India is undoubtedly federal, in which the Centre and the States share sovereignty.

According to RL Watts, Indian federalism since 1950 has been a mixture of centralization and decentralisation. The decisive role of the states has increased and the role of the states has increased in establishing the central authority. Thus federalism in India has deepened further.

Rashid Uddin Khan is of the opinion that Indian federalism is a system in which the structural-functional balance is inclined towards the centre. Regarding the Indian federal system, by the Supreme Court, S.R. In Bomai Vs Union of India 1994 case, the decision given is very important. In which the Supreme Court has considered the federal system as the basic structure of the Indian Constitution.

Secondly, the Indian system is not federal

Ivor Jennings has termed the Indian system as a federation which has a tendency of excessive centralization. K. Santhanam, like Jennings, termed it as supreme federalism (chantanuvandaj thmakmatanspeudh) because of the tendency of centralization in the Indian federal government. But K.C. Wheer considers India as semi-federal and his concept is most popular. According to him, India is a federal state bearing the characteristics of a unitary system. At present, various forms of federal system are prevalent, among them India is also a form of federalism in itself. In the words of Dr. D. D. Basu, "The Constitution of India is neither purely federal nor purely unitary. It is a combination of both. It is a new type of union or federated state. It contains the principle that national interest should be supreme in spite of having a federation.

Various Forms of Indian Federalism

Indian federalism has been dynamic in nature. Due to various political upheavals since independence till now, different forms or patterns of federalism are visible in India. All these formats are not limited to any one-time frame, but they have also been a part of Indian federalism from time to time in a mixed form -

1. Centralized federalism -

After independence, the central leadership was in the hands of outstanding leaders like Patel and the public opinion was with the Congress. In Indian politics till 1967, the competing parties of the Congress were negligible and the Congress was handling India as an organization where the centre was everything. Centre and state relations at this time were actually like relations between the Congress at the centre and the Congress in the states, and differences were resolved at the party level itself.

2. Cooperative Federalism or Cooperative Federalism

Grenville Austin has termed Indian federalism as 'cooperative federalism'. In cooperative federalism, centre-state relations are not horizontal and participation of states in national development and policy making is ensured. At present, the formation of NITI Aayog gives character to cooperative federalism. Apart from this, there are Finance Commission, Inter-State

Committees, Zonal Councils, National Development Councils, institutions which enhance cooperation in centre and state relations.

3. Federalism of Bargaining -

In the era of coalition governments, the role of regional organizations and parties increased a lot in national politics. In the 1990s, regional parties came to play a decisive role in the central government. This form of Indian federalism is called bargaining federalism where various regional parties try to impose local interests on national politics and resort to bargaining to get their demands met from the central government, hence Morris Jones India has been called "bargain federalism".

4. Competitive federalism-

This form of federalism became visible after the 1991 economic reforms in India. In this, an environment of competition developed between the centre and the state and between the states for investment and financial benefits. This positive competition accelerates the process of development and reduces the financial dependence of the states on the centre. In this, all the states organize investment conferences in their respective states, strengthen their infrastructure, in the last years Maharashtra, Madhya Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, Gujarat etc. have made commendable efforts to promote tourism in their states, due to which Speed up the development of the state.

Centre-State Relations: Controversial Topics

As a result of the dynamics of Centre and State relations in India, disputes have been seen between the Union and the States on many subjects. Several committees have been formed to give a positive shape to the Centre-State relations. First Administrative Reforms Commission (1966) was constituted. Similarly, Rajmanna Committee (1969), Anandpur Sahib Resolution (1973), West Bengal Memorandum (1977), Sarkaria Commission (1983), Punchhi Commission (2007), etc. were constituted. Despite the formation of these committees, there are some issues in Indian centre and state relations which have always been controversial.

1. Role of the Governor

There is a provision for the post of Governor under Article 153 of the Indian Constitution. The Governor is appointed by the President under Article 155. Questions have been raised since 1953 on the role of the Governor. In 1959, the Kerala government headed by Nambudiripad was dismissed. The Governor has always been seen as the representative of the Centre and the Central Governments have also been misusing this position.

Apart from this, Articles 200 and 201 give privilege to the Governor that he can keep any bill for the approval of the President. The use of this privilege has always been viewed with suspicion by the state governments. Article 163 gives the Governor the power to exercise his discretion on various subjects like inviting the leader of the majority party for the post of Chief Minister in case of doubt etc.

2. Excessive use of President's rule

Articles 356 and 365 make the central government more powerful. Article 356 allows that in case of failure of constitutional machinery in a state, the central government can take over the administration of the state by dismissing the state government. Article 365 provides that even if a state fails to comply with the directions given by the Centre, the administration of the state can be handed over to the Central Government.

The political use of the above powers has made these provisions controversial. In 1977, President's rule was imposed on the Congress states by the Janata government and it was also used by Indira Gandhi in the decade of 1980s and even at present, the rights of the states are being challenged on the basis of fulfilment of political interests.

3. All India Services

All India Services play an important role in maintaining administrative relations, but their appointment, dismissal, jurisdiction etc. have been the cause of dispute between the centre and the state relations. It is the allegation of the state governments that the centre controls the

administrative officers in relation to the All-India Services and the power to take all important decisions is also with the centre itself, due to which the officers are more inclined towards the central government even if they are appointed in the state government.

4. Legislative Relations

Legislative relations are mentioned in Part 11 of the Constitution from Articles 245 to 255. Article 245 empowers the Central Government to make laws for any part of the country. The centre has got wide powers for state administration, which it has been using from time to time.

Proclamation of emergency, international treaties, the subject of misuse of President's rule, many powers have also been given to the centre in constitutional amendment. Article 249 provides that the Rajya Sabha can make laws on subjects listed in the State List by passing a bill with a two-thirds majority. Therefore, practically the centre is capable of interfering in the state administration when necessary.

5. Financial Relations Disputes

Part XII of the Constitution, Articles 268 to 293 deal with financial relations. Disputes related to revenue distribution; sources of income are important in financial relations. In the past years, the issue of favouritism in giving grants to the states by the central government is also very serious. At present, the Goods and Services Act 2017 has also been a very controversial subject. Through this, the nature of Indian federalism has also changed. It is noteworthy that the financial resources of the states were very limited in the original constitution, but after the implementation of the Goods and Services Tax Act, the power of the states in the financial sector has decreased considerably and the jurisdiction of the central government has increased. Regarding this point also, some states have been demanding changes in it, such as West Bengal. At the time of Corona epidemic, it was seen that the Central Government did not give the share of Goods and Services Tax to the states on time, due to which the financial crisis of the states in the Covid pandemic increased further. In this context, some states believe that its distribution should be on a rational basis in which the increasing dependence of the states on the centre can be reduced.

Indian Federalism in Practice: Current Perspectives

Out of all the countries that became independent after independence, very few countries could keep intact their constitution and the political system established by it. The federal system has successfully handled various diversities, demands in India and has also been successful in keeping it stable. The Indian federal system accommodated the rights and demands of the different states of the country. For the past years, mainly cooperative, unitary and bargaining federalism has been more prevalent in Indian federalism. New issues have emerged in the centre-state relations and concerns have been expressed by various states regarding centralization of power. Collaborative federalism like setting up of NITI Aayog by disbanding the Planning Commission, giving more financial assistance to the states by accepting the 14th Finance Commission's recommendation of ten percent increase in the revenue share of the states, Centre through Goods and Services Act 2017 And strengthening the state's financial partnership, etc. But a second aspect of these reforms is also observable in the centre and state relations. Mainly in the Goods and Services Act 2017, the subject of payment of compensation amount to the states is very serious. Not giving the funds to the states on time further weakens their financial condition, among other subjects, the decision of demonetisation by the central government is also important. Where such a big decision was taken without assessing the status and capability of the states.

Similarly, the withdrawal of its special status from the state of Kashmir, the deadlock on agricultural laws, questioning the proceedings of the Central Bureau of Investigation by various states, alleging favouritism in the process of the Election Commission by the states, etc. are such topics where in the last years, the centre and state relations in Indian federalism have not been balanced and a sense of mutual distrust has developed.

At present, even during the Covid pandemic, the disaster management of the central government has reduced the co-operation between the states. The states believe that the central government did not

take timely decisions and did not provide financial grants and assistance related to health services. The most important point is the national level lockdown where it was implemented without assessing the condition of the states. The financial, political, administrative crisis in the Indian federal system deepened further during the Covid health crisis. From all these topics, the trend of increasing centralization in Indian federalism becomes clear. Louis Tillin, the director of the King's Indian Institute, has recently said in his interview that this time is a decisive moment for Indian federalism, where the tendency of centralization has increased rapidly in the past years. Therefore, there is a need to increase the participation of states in Indian federalism. There is a need to review the present federal system on the basis of constitutional provisions.

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